

YOUTH ON THE MOVE: EDITORIAL MANAGEMENT AND NEWS REPORTING

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***Abstract:** Media is going through a massive change globally as an impact of burgeoning information and telecommunication technology. Increased global ICT penetration and media convergence are posing new challenges to media organizations, news desks and staff. In this backdrop tertiary educational institutions need to calibrate their study programs to reflect these developments. This paper highlights how four institutions in the Netherlands, Germany, Turkey and Norway are developing their study programs in Media and Communication Studies and in Journalism Studies to meet some of these challenges.*

***Keywords:** ICT, media convergence, iPhones, iPads, Androids, integrated broadband, information superhighway, intensive program, paywall, web platform, blogazine.*

Introduction

Increased global ICT penetration and media convergence are posing new challenges to media organizations, news desks and staff. Tertiary educational institutions must therefore calibrate their study programs to reflect these developments. This paper highlights how four institutions in the Netherlands, Germany, Turkey and Norway are developing their study programs in Media and Communication Studies and in Journalism Studies to meet some of these challenges.

Converge or perish

Media convergence can be interpreted in many ways, all involving the extent to which news organizations share news content with a) other news organization, b) another medium in their own organization, c) sharing staff d) promoting other media for which they produce or from which they receive content (Chapman & Nuttall 2011, p. 165). Media convergence is a powerful driving force in all media development today and can come about when e.g. media companies integrate functions or units vertically and/or horizontally. Media convergence has been facilitated by the rapid technological developments over the last decade, especially the development of online

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media and news distribution through a variety of platforms, most recently iPhones, iPads and Androids. While there are still considerable digital gaps among and within many of the world's countries, overall ICT penetration is increasing worldwide, as data from the International Telecommunications Union show (figure 1).

Figure 1: Global ICT developments 2001-2011 (ITU 2012)

Integrated broadband and the so-called “information superhighway” make it possible for journalists and news desks around the world to produce content once for instant online delivery across a variety of platforms such as print newspaper pages, websites, blogs, podcast, radio and TV news bulletins. This new technological environment poses many challenges, including new demands on editorial management and news reporting in online media.

Youth on the Move

At the ICCMTD conference in Istanbul in May 2012, a paper was presented by four authors from the Netherlands, Germany, Turkey and Norway on their plans to launch a joint, online weekly magazine staffed by students (Boers, Ercan, Rinsdorf & Vaagan 2012). The name of the planned magazine - *Youth on the Move* - corresponds to one of the flagship initiatives in the European Union's growth strategy EU 2020. Following the conference, the authors in June 2012 secured funding from the European Union to start organizing annual 10-day intensive programs (IPs) for a three-year period 2013-2015. The three EU/IPs are scheduled in February 2013 in the Netherlands, in

February 2014 in Norway and in February 2015 in Germany. In the first IP in Amsterdam in February 2013, six students and two teachers from each of the four countries will spend 10 days together and work on launching the magazine. The students will be third or fourth year undergraduates in Media and Communication Studies.

This paper highlights some features of the planned weekly online magazine. Following the conference, the authors in June 2012 secured funding from the European Union to start organizing annual 10-day intensive programs (IPs) for a three-year period 2013-2015. In the first IP in Amsterdam in February 2013 has already been held. Six students and two teachers from each of the four countries spent 10 days together and worked on launching the magazine. The students were third or fourth year undergraduates in Media and Communication Studies. As per decision, public domain software (Wordpress) would be used for publishing the magazine as well as for planning and student interaction (Moodle).

Editorial Management

Converging media will increase the importance of some existing professional skills while the need for some new skills emerge (Bull, 2010; Long & Wall, 2009). Compared with the former print and nascent online news environment at the beginning of the new millennium (Tumber, 1999; Patterson & Patterson, 2003; Allan, 2006) today's media environment with online news, multiplatform publishing, user-generated content and emerging "paywalls" requires more from editors, management and journalists (Achtenhagen & Raviola, 2009; Bartsova, 2009; Allan & Thorsen, 2009). To be successful in today's media environment, improved skills and competencies are needed in multi-modal editorial planning and cross-channel development of news stories.

As print readership is declining and online readership rapidly increasing, business models are changing. Advertisers are placing less money in print media and more in online media. Online reader preferences are shifting towards mobile phones and iPads. In this environment all levels of management must have a firm understanding of the specific demands of different media channels in presenting cross-media or multimodal news to audiences. At the same time more newspapers are introducing digital subscription plans ("paywalls") where readers are asked to pay for unlimited access to content. This makes it mandatory for a successful cross-media outlet to have management with entrepreneurial skills and successful digital

business models that can accommodate integrated plans and implementation of media asset management and integrated workflows (Croteau & Hoynes, 2006; Long & Wall, 2009).

Today, all management and staff levels must therefore embody a level of web competence, especially improved understanding of key technologies, programming and integration of different media channels into one web platform (Vukanovic, 2009; Chan-Olmsted, 2011). This includes social media where e.g. in Scandinavia social media represent around 60% of primary sources in published news stories. Sensing the potential of Twitter for branding among elite users, several newspapers in Norway now require their editors and journalists to include the name of the media channel in the Twitter address. This shows not only the need for editors, management and journalists to manage innovation processes (Ofsti, 2011) but also to handle media ethics, privacy and use of sources (Vaagan, 2011).

During the intensive program (IP), students will therefore be introduced to how to launch, run and staff a successful online magazine directed at the international consumer and business community and develop a competent, international staff of all-round journalists. The staff of media organizations is often homogenous and the innovative character of this IP includes tapping the synergies of four different countries and cultures in a collective effort. Depending on the journal's size, ownership and legal framework, the chief editor at least in smaller magazines is often also chief executive officer, reporting to the board or owner(s). As chief editor, she/he is also legally responsible for all content and for all editorial decisions. The successful chief editor will know how to strike a fine balance between the commercial and editorial elements, which sometimes means resisting interference from the proprietor in the running of the magazine. At the same time, the editor needs to coach and inspire a variety of competent journalists. The journalists of a successful online magazine must also be able to deliver continuously high-quality reports and coverage of key issues and events, including user-generated content such as blogs and crowd sourcing, all related to the journal's editorial profile.

Managing a successful online magazine requires multiple skills and competences on the part of the entire staff. Students from the four participant countries will role-play as editor and be confronted with tough editorial and ethical dilemmas. Students will develop skills and competences preparing them to work as successful editors and journalists in a multi-cultural context.

During the IP, lectures and role play will focus on the requirements especially of the editor in terms of creating and managing a successful online magazine, in the cross-pressure between owners, market, competitors, advertisers on the one hand, and on the other hand editorial responsibilities including audiences, legal, ethical challenges, accurate and truthful reporting as well as forging a team of competent journalists from different cultures all producing continuously high-quality cross-media content.

News writing and reporting

Today, the successful journalist must project his/her narrative skills to a cross-media environment and write also for mobile phones and iPads. This means shooting, cropping, editing and captioning pictures; recording, editing and publishing audio reports and podcasts; shooting and editing video, creating packages and streaming live reports, interacting with user-generated content; interviewing and doing online research; sub-editing, proofreading and headlining, including search engine optimization; geo-tagging, geo-coding and geo-broadcasting (Bull, 2010; Silvia & Anzur, 2011). Cross-media news writing and storytelling are different from producing for broadcast media and print news. While broadcast news offers immediacy and impact (sound, visuals and emotions), print news offers depth, detail and permanence. Compared with these, today's web journalism is based on demand, it is interactive and innovative. For over 100 years print and broadcast journalists have used a narrative style that follows a linear process of news reporting and writing. This involves first getting the story, then pitching the story to the editor or news director, then generating research, doing interviews and reporting the final story. In writing across media one adds elements to this process by creating a non-linear approach, which means that instead of developing a rigidly structured single narrative you choose to navigate through the elements of story by using a combination of text, still photographs, video clips, audio, graphics, and interactivity such as polls or blogs on a website in such a fashion that each medium is complementary. In this way different parts of a story are told using different media in the most engaging and informative way (Silvia & Anzur, 2011). The new media environment is also trans-national which necessitates increased understanding of the process of globalization and intercultural competence, including European integration and the goals of EU2020 such as "Youth on the Move".

During the IP, students will therefore work as journalists, editors and staff and cover a variety of events and issues all related to improving educational and vocational cooperation among participating institutions, increasing

student mobility and ultimately student employability in the European labor market and beyond. The innovative aspect of the IP includes encouraging students to immerse themselves in a cross-cultural working environment and benefit from synergies through co-writing and co-editing content across multiple media platforms, including social media. Students will benefit from being familiarized with different institutional online magazines and blogazines in participating countries.

Students will achieve enhanced knowledge, improved skills and competencies in reaching out to digitally literate audiences through producing texts with video, audio and pictures in multimedia packages. In this manner students will become familiarized with several aspects of media convergence: the integrative aspect (the merging of different technologies and industries to create new forms of cultural product and new modes of production and delivery e.g. iPhones, iPads, Androids) and also the divergence aspect (the flow of content across multiple media platforms, the cooperation between multiple media industries and the migratory behavior of media audiences, who will go anywhere for desired entertainment experience)

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